

CAMPUS JOURNALISM PRACTICES AMONG STATE UNIVERSITIES OF CALABARZON

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ABSTRACT

Campus Journalism plays a huge part in Philippine Education. The management of the Student Publication led to the use of campus journalism practices to achieve journalism goals and objectives of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) pursuant to the Campus Journalism Act of 1991. This study aimed to describe the respondents, identify the challenges, and assess the campus journalism practices in state universities of CALABARZON. The researcher utilized the descriptive method of research using qualitative and quantitative approaches. There was a total of 437 respondents from the 5 state universities. A researcher-made questionnaire and focus group discussion (FGD) were utilized in the study. Weighted mean, frequency/percentage, ranking, and Chi-square of Independence were the statistical tools used. Based on the data gathered, it was found out that the campus journalism practices used in planning, management, production and distribution, and participation during competitions were moderately manifested. However, some of the campus journalism practices in budgeting were least manifested. The findings further revealed the most common challenges encountered by campus journalists were most commonly regarding printing and distribution of editions, budgeting transparency, and management of student publication funds. The results suggested the creation of a creative management plan for the improvement and upgrade of campus journalism practices of HEIs.

Keywords: campus journalism practices, management, creative management plan, Philippines